

TEACHING COMPETENCE OF TEACHER WORKING ON SECONDARY SCHOOL OF MAYURBHANJ DISTRICT

Shaktijeet Nayak

Assistant professor in Educational Studies, M.P.C Autonomous College, Baripada, Mayurbhanj, Odisha. Mail Id- nayakshaktijeet@gmail.com

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Abstract

The present study titled "Teaching Competence of Teachers Working in Secondary Schools of Mayurbhanj District" aimed to access and compare the teaching competency levels of secondary school teachers with respect to gender, qualification, experience, and age. The study adopted a descriptive survey method involving 150 teachers from 11 secondary schools in Mayurbhanj District, selected through purposive sampling. A self-developed teaching competency questionnaire was used to collect data, covering dimensions like content knowledge, instructional strategies, classroom management, student engagement, ICT integration, and assessment and feedback. The Shapiro-Wilk test indicated a significant difference in the variance of teaching competency scores across different groups ($p=.000$), implying the need for non-parametric testing. The study applied the Mann-Whitney U test for analysis. The findings revealed that female teachers demonstrated slightly higher teaching competency levels compared to male teachers, but the difference was not statistically significant. Similarly, teaching competency showed no significant variation with respect to gender, qualification, experience, and age. The study concludes that teaching competency among secondary school teachers in Mayurbhanj District remains consistent across demographic variables. It suggests the need for continuous professional development and training programs to further enhance teaching competencies. Future studies could be conducted with larger sample sizes for broader generalizations.

Key Words: *Teaching competence, Secondary school teacher, Classroom management.*

INTRODUCTION

The term 'competence' first appeared in a text authored by Craig C. Lundberg in 1972 titled "Planning the Executive Development Program", and then in David McClelland's seminal 1973 treatise entitled, "Testing for Competence Rather than for Intelligence". According to his research, traditional academic aptitude and knowledge content rarely help to predict on-

job performance. He went on to argue that the real predictors of job performance are a set of underlying personal characteristics or ‘competencies.’ McClelland's concept of competency has been the key driver of the competency movement and competency-based education. Niemi and Sihvonen (2006) argued that “The social and economic well-being of a society is definitely dependent on the quality of education outcomes, and this is related to teacher competence”. Teachers’ competences involve the diverse roles of teachers at different levels of personal, school, local community, and professional networks, covering the entire spectrum of their profession (Hager & McIntyre, 2006). Teaching competence encompasses a teacher's ability to plan lessons, represent subjects, manage classrooms, and assess student performance. It involves handling materials, controlling learning programs, assessing progress, and controlling the classroom. It also involves employing pedagogical techniques, recognizing students' abilities, and modifying instruction accordingly (Sudirman, et.al,2019). The **Secondary Education Commission (1952- 53)** highlights that teacher competence as mastery of subject knowledge, effective teaching methods, ability to inspire students, and fostering critical thinking. “Teaching competency is those skills, concepts and attitudes needed by teachers for the act of instruction in an educational institution.” (Good, 1973). Houston (1987) stated that “competencies are the requirements of a competency-based teacher education, which includes the knowledge, skills and values the student must demonstrate for successful completion of the performance.”

COMPONENT OF TEACHING COMPETENCE:

Figure-1. Components of Teaching Competence (Sudirman, et.al,2019)

Content knowledge refers to a teacher's thorough understanding of the subject being taught. This includes the essential facts, concepts, principles, and methods of the discipline, enabling the teacher to convey accurate and meaningful information to students, address misconceptions, and encourage deeper learning.

Instructional strategies refer to the methods and techniques teachers use to deliver lessons, engage students, and help them understand and apply the content effectively.

Student engagement refers to involving students in the teaching process, asking them to read or work during class, and stimulating their thinking. It includes using their responses in lessons, encouraging presentations, having them solve problems on the board, promoting peer learning, and assigning group activities.

Classroom management refers to creating a positive environment, encouraging questions, maintaining discipline, and keeping students engaged. It also involves listening patiently, treating students equally, and sharing resources.

ICT integration refers to using technology in teaching, such as PowerPoint presentations, video links, and e-learning materials. It involves using video clips for demonstrations, encouraging students to explore online sources, and applying ICT for assessments. Additionally, teachers use educational mobile apps to support teaching and learning.

Assessment and feedback refer to asking questions to all students, appreciating their responses, and using a variety of questions. It refers to using assessment results to plan future lessons and remedial classes, as well as using student feedback for personal improvement. Additionally, it refers to asking questions after each learning point, assigning practical tasks, and using portfolios or projects for assessment.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

After reviewing all the literature, it is evidenced that there are a number of studies found related to reading habits India and also in abroad. Manuel et al (2023) found that teachers are high competence in instructional preparation and delivery, moderate competence in assessment techniques, and lower competence in the implementation of teaching methods during instruction. Jankovic and StanojevicGocic (2023) revealed that lecturers hold a positive perception of their teaching competencies in relation to teacher leadership and content knowledge. Suhail Ahmed Khan (2021) found revealed that Teaching Competency and attitude towards creative teaching has difference exists in percentage of trainee-teachers. The teaching competency of trainee-teachers is found a significance differences between the Pedagogical groups. Attitude of trainee-teachers towards creative teaching mean have

significant difference exists in their Gender, Caste, and Qualifications bases. Prasad et.al, (2022) revealed that there is need for improving the quality of the education system by identifying faculty abilities essential for effective recruiting, training, and performance management in higher educational institutions. Thao (2020) found that more significant factors affecting the teaching profession in the Modern Indian context is the teacher working in secondary education with respect to gender, qualification, experience, age. Nbina (2012) revealed that There is a significant correlation between teachers' competence and students' academic performance in chemistry, with qualified and experienced teachers performing better than unqualified and inexperienced teachers. Qadhiet.al (2020) found that revealed female teachers are more competent in teaching than the male teachers. It is also found that competency of teacher's above 40 is higher than the teachers age up to 40. Thus, competency of experienced teachers is higher than inexperienced teachers. Rajeswari and Sree (2017) found that there is no significant difference in the teaching competency of teacher educators with regard to gender, age, qualification, experience.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To study the level of teaching competence of teachers working in secondary schools.
- To compare the teaching competence of teachers working in secondary schools with respect to gender, qualification, experience, age.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- H₀: There is no significant difference in the teaching competence of teachers working in secondary schools with respect to gender.
- H₀: There is no significant difference in the teaching competence of teachers working in secondary schools with respect to qualification.
- H₀: There is no significant difference in the teaching competence of teachers working in secondary schools with respect to experience.
- H₀: There is no significant difference in the teaching competence of teachers working in secondary schools with respect to age.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Keeping in view the nature of the study, objective type of data was collected. The investigator has followed the **Descriptive Survey method** for collection of data. The investigator herself moved from school to school and met teachers. This study is concerned on Teaching competence of Teacher working in secondary school of Mayurbhanj district. The data for this research were in descriptive form rather than numerical or inferential. Teachers, head teachers

were the prime data for this research. Therefore, the researcher tried to explore the interaction between teacher to get the valuable data for her research. In the present study the population constituted all the secondary school of Mayurbhanj District. For the present study the researcher has been selected 11 no. of secondary schools from Mayurbhanj District. For the present study a total number of 150 teachers selected as sample by following purposive sampling technique. Out of 150 teachers 80 were male and another 70 were female teachers. The investigator will used self- developed teaching competence questionnaire (closed ended) for data collection. The 3-point scale including option like Maximum (3), Moderate (2), Minimum (1). The scoring is done by awarding marks 3 to 1. The investigator will give the questionnaire form to the sample group and collect the data. The collected data will be analyzed with the help of descriptive statistics like percentage, mean, median, mode, standard deviation (SD), maximum, minimum, skewness, and kurtosis, and inferential statistics. The collected data will be analyses with the help of MS Excel and SPSS software.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The interpretation of data is based on careful, logical and critical examination of results of analysis which is further based on the nature of problem, objectives and research question of the study. The objectives of the study are;

1. To study and compare the teaching Competence of teachers working in secondary schools.
2. To compare the teaching Competence of teachers working in secondary schools with reference to gender, qualification, experience and age.

TABLE-1: Shapiro-Wilk Test of Normality

variable	statistic	df	Sig.
Teaching competency	.946	150	.000

Figure-2: Graphical Normality Test of secondary schools for Teaching Competence.

There is a significant difference in the variances of teaching competency scores across the groups tested. The spread (variance) of teaching competency scores is not the same across different groups. This violates the assumption of equal variance."The graph shows non probability curve so that we can conduct non parametric test for finding the result.

TABLE-2: Descriptive Statistics for Comparing Teaching Competence of Male and Female Teachers in Secondary Schools

Measures	N	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	SEM
Groups							
Male	63	116.97	117	6.773	.051	.438	.853
Female	87	119.89	119	8.025	1.034	3.503	.860

The table-1 reveals those statistics for two groups, males (N=63) and females (N=87). The male group has a mean score of 116.97, with a standard deviation of 6.773, indicating a moderately spread distribution. The female group has a slightly higher mean of 119.89 and a higher standard deviation of 8.025, suggesting high variability in scores. Both groups show positive skewness, with females exhibiting a stronger skew (1.034) compared to males (0.051), indicating that female scores are more concentrated at the lower end. The male group also has lower kurtosis (.438), suggesting a less peaked distribution, while the female group is more platykurtic (3.503), indicating a flatter distribution. The standard error of the mean is slightly lower for males (.853) compared to females (.860), reflecting a less precise estimate of the mean for the female group. It can be concluded that female teachers tend to have more consistent and higher teaching competency levels than their male counterparts. The teaching competency of male and female teaches is graphically presented in following box plot.

Figure-3: Box plot on Competencies of Teachers in secondary schools with respect to gender

TABLE-3: Mann-Whitney Test for Comparing Competence of Male and Female Teachers in Secondary Schools

Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	z-value	Sig.	Remarks
Male	63	66.87	2197.000	2.073	.038	NS
Female	87	81.75				

*NS=Not Significant at 0.05 level

The table-2 indicates that female teachers (N = 87) have a mean rank of 81.75, while male teachers (N =63) have a mean rank of 66.87, suggesting that female teachers generally have higher teaching competency scores. The Mann-Whitney U value is 2197.00, with a z-value of 2.073, indicate a statistically significant difference in teaching competency at 0.05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference in teaching competency of teachers working in secondary schools with reference to gender” is accepted. Hence, it can be stated that female teachers have similar teaching competency with male teachers in secondary schools.

TABLE-4: Descriptive Statistics for Comparing Teaching Competency of Teachers in Secondary Schools in Terms of Age

Measure Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	SEM
Age below 30	81	119.37	118.0	8.473	.996	3.155	.941
Age above 30	69	117.83	117.00	6.487	.144	.638	.781

The table-3 reveals that the data compares two age groups: individuals below 30 years (N=81) and those above 30 years (N=69). The group below 30 has a mean score of 119.37 with a standard deviation of 8.473, indicating higher variability. The group age above 30 years has a slightly lower mean of 117.83 and a similar standard deviation of 6.487, suggesting comparable spread in scores. Both groups display skewness, with the younger group having a slightly higher skewness (.996) compared to the older group (0.144), indicating a stronger concentration of lower scores in the younger group. The kurtosis values are close for both groups, with the lower group showing slightly more peaked Ness (3.155) compared to the higher group (0.638). The standard error of the mean is larger for the younger group (8.473), indicating less precision in estimating the mean for this group compared to the older group, which has a smaller SEM of 0.781. It can be concluded that age above 30 years teachers tend

to have more consistent and higher teaching competency levels than their age below 30 years teacher’s counterparts.

Figure-4: Box plot on Competencies of Teachers in secondary schools with respect to age.

TABLE-5: Mann-Whitney Test for Comparing Teaching Competency in Terms of Age in Secondary Schools

Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	z-value	Sig.	Remarks
Age below 30	81	78.30	2567.500	.857	.391	SIGNI
Age above 30	69	72.21				

*NS=Not Significant at 0.05 level.

The table-4 indicates that age below 30 years teachers (N = 81) have a mean rank of 78.30, while age above 30 years teachers (N =69) have a mean rank of 72.21. The Mann-Whitney U value is 2567.500, with a z-value of 0.857, indicate a statistically not significant difference in teaching competency at 0.05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference in teaching competency of teachers working in secondary schools with reference to age” is accepted. Hence, it can be stated that age below 30 years teachers have similar teaching competency with age above 30 years teachers in secondary schools.

TABLE-6: Descriptive Statistics for Comparing Teaching Competency of Teachers in Secondary Schools in Terms of Qualification

Measure Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	SEM
U.g. with B.ED.	66	119.12	117.00	9.236	1.089	2.304	1.137
P.g. with B.ED.	84	118.30	118.50	6.135	.462	.314	.669

The data compares two educational groups: undergraduate with a B.Ed., teacher (N=66) and postgraduate with a B.Ed., teacher. (N=84). The undergraduate group has a mean score of 119.12 and a standard deviation of 9.236, indicating moderate variability in scores. The postgraduate group has a slightly higher mean of 118.50 but a lower standard deviation of 6.135, suggesting more variability in this group. The postgraduate group exhibits skewness (0.462), indicating a slight concentration of lower scores, while the undergraduate group has a higher skewness (1.089), suggesting a stronger concentration of lower scores and a more pronounced right tail. The kurtosis for the undergraduate group (2.304) is higher, indicating a more peaked distribution compared to the postgraduate group (0.314), which is relatively flatter. The standard error of the mean is notably higher for the undergraduate group (1.137), indicating less precision in estimating the mean for this group compared to the postgraduate group (0.669). It can be concluded that postgraduate with B.Ed. teachers tend to have more consistent and higher teaching competency levels than their undergraduate with B.Ed. teachers in secondary schools.

Figure-5: Box plot on Competencies of Teachers in secondary schools with respect to qualification.

Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	z-value	Sig.	Remarks
UG with B.Ed	66	74.80	2726.000	0.174	0.862	NS
PG with B.Ed	84	76.05				

NS=Not Significant at 0.05 level.

Mann-Whitney Test for Comparing Teaching competency in Terms of Qualification in Secondary Schools.

This indicates that undergraduate with B.Ed. teachers (N = 66) have a mean rank of 74.80, while postgraduate with B.Ed. teachers (N =84) have a mean rank of 76.05. The Mann-Whitney U value is 2726.00, with a z-value of .174, indicate a statistically not significant difference in teaching competency at 0.05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference in teaching competency of teachers working in secondary schools with reference to qualification” is accepted. Hence, it can be stated that undergraduate with B.Ed. teachers have similar teaching competency with postgraduate with B.Ed. teachers in secondary schools.

TABLE-7: Descriptive Statistics for Comparing Teaching Competency of Teachers in Secondary Schools in Terms of Experience

Measure Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	SEM
1-10 years	81	118.12	117.00	6.840	.140	.689	.760
Above 10 years	69	119.29	118.00	8.489	1.237	3.979	1.022

The data compares two experience groups: teachers with 1-10 years of experience (N=81) and those with above 10 years of experience (N=69). The group with 1-10 years of experience has a mean score of 118.12 and a standard deviation of 6.840, indicating moderate variability in scores. The group with above 10 years of experience has a slightly higher mean of 119.29 and a higher standard deviation of 8.489, suggesting a wider spread in scores. Both groups exhibit skewness, with the 1-10 years group having a skewness of 0.140 and the above 10 years group having a slightly higher skewness of 1.237, indicating a mild concentration of lower scores in both groups. The kurtosis values indicate that the above 10 years group (3.979) is more peaked than the 1-10 years group (0.689), which has a flatter distribution. The standard error of the mean is higher for the above 10 years group (1.022), indicating more precision in estimating the mean compared to the 1-10 years group, which has a higher SEM of 1.022. It can be concluded that teachers with above 10 years of experience tend to have more consistent and higher teaching competency levels than teachers with 1-10 years of experience in secondary schools.

Figure-6: Box plot on Competencies of Teachers in secondary schools with respect to Teaching Experience.

TABLE-8: Mann-Whitney Test for Comparing Teaching competency in Terms of Experience in Secondary Schools

Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	z-value	Sig.	Remarks
1-10 years	69	74.12	2683.000	.421	.674	NS
Above 10 years	81	77.12				

*NS=Not Significant at 0.05 level.

The table-7 indicates that teachers with 1-10 years of experience (N = 69) have a mean rank of 74.12, while teachers above 10 years of experience (N = 81) have a mean rank of 77.12. The Mann-Whitney U value is 2683.000, with a z-value of .421, indicate a statistically not significant difference in teaching competency at 0.05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference in teaching competency of teachers working in secondary schools with reference to experience” is accepted. Hence, it can be stated that teachers with 1-10 years of experience have similar teaching competency with teachers above 10 years of experience in secondary schools.

MAJOR FINDINGS

- There is no significance difference between male and female Teacher working in secondary school towards Teaching competence. Thus, the hypothesis-1 there exist no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers towards Teaching competence.
- There is no significant difference in the teaching competence of teachers working in secondary schools with respect to qualification.

- There is no significant difference in the teaching competence of teachers working in secondary schools with respect to experience.
- There is no significant difference in the teaching competence of teachers working in secondary schools with respect to age.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULT

The present study revealed that there was no significant difference in the competencies of teachers in secondary school based on gender at the 0.05 level. This result is supported by previous research studies (Tzafilkou et.al., 2023; Garzon et. al., 2021). However, (Verma and Dahiya 2015) found that male teachers have greater competencies than female teachers because they participate in more professional development programs. The present study found that there is a significant difference in the competencies of teachers working in secondary schools based on qualifications at the 0.05 levels. This is in accordance with the research study conducted by (Mahmood et al.,2023; Asis et al.,2023; Krishan & Fernandes ,2023; Dominguez & Bezanilla 2021). This contrasts with studies conducted by Zeb, Begum, & Ullah (2022), Rodriguez et al. (2022), and Bhattacharjee & Carri (2020), which indicated that teachers with P.G. with B.Ed. qualifications have higher competencies than those with U.G. with B.Ed. qualifications, due to their greater use of ICT in the teaching-learning process. The present study indicated that there is a significant difference in competencies among teachers working in secondary schools with reference to experience at the 0.05 level. This is in accordance with the research studies conducted by (Swain 2024; Hassan & Mirza 2021). This is in contrast with the studies conducted by (Zeb et al., 2022; Manisha D.A., 2022; Siregar & Soni Mirizon, 2021; Kasule et al., 2021; Hoque et al., 2021) who indicated that there is no significant difference in competencies among teachers with reference to experience because all teachers have access to similar professional development opportunities, institutional resources, and teaching frameworks

The present study found that there is a significant difference in competencies among teachers working in secondary schools with reference to age at the 0.05 level. These findings were not supported by (Swain 2024; Radhamani & Kalaivani 2023), who revealed that there is no significant difference in competencies among teachers with reference to age due to equal access to resources, continuous professional growth, cross-age collaboration.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLIFICATION

- It will help the Institutions to provide opportunities for teachers to refine their skills.
- It will help the schools and policymakers need to recognize and address systemic

barriers that may hinder teacher competence.

- It will help the teachers to enhance enthusiasm for learning inspire students to adopt a similar attitude.
- Competence includes the ability to instill a growth mindset and resilience in students.
- It will help Competent teachers to adept, recognizing and addressing diverse student needs, including those related to culture, language, socioeconomic background, and learning disabilities.
- It will develop competence in classroom management ensures discipline, organization, and respect, promoting a safe and conducive learning atmosphere.
- It will help to create competent teachers using effective instructional strategies, differentiated learning, and formative assessments to enhance student learning.

CONCLUSION

Today's revolutionary moment demands a teacher who is both dedicated and skilled. One of the most important factors for the success of education and schools has been shown to be the competency of teachers. The performance of teachers at work is intimately linked to their competency. A skilled educator can see into the future of the prospective pupil and do everything in their power to realise the dream of the nation. According to the current study, there are notable differences between male and female secondary teachers in terms of their teaching competency, teaching aptitude, emotional intelligence, and adjustment. This difference may be explained by the interdependence of the variables. Male secondary school instructors were determined to be better than their female counterparts because they are more energetic, physically fit, enthusiastic, and conceptually aware. Additionally, they have the bravery, self-assurance, self-control, and self-regulation necessary to improve their cognitive knowledge. The emotional intelligence, flexibility, teaching competency, and teaching aptitude of secondary school teachers were unaffected by religion. The secondary school teachers' teaching competency were all unaffected by their credentials. It has been discovered that secondary school teacher in the science and art streams are equal to teaching competence. This result showed that secondary school teachers' competence was unaffected by their qualifications. Teachers in secondary schools in the science stream were better adjusted than those in the art stream. The high levels of emotional intelligence, teaching aptitude, and adaptability were the main predictors of teaching competency. Teaching competency with emotional intelligence was given the highest weight in the model, followed by teaching

aptitude and adjustment, based on the standardised regression coefficients of the predictors and their connection.

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